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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling
Approaches

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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ArtiSaneFood – Biopreservation and Risk Modelling Approaches: Book of Abstracts

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Evaluation of the Influence of Intrinsic Properties on the Microbiological Quality of Traditional Portuguese *Transmontano* Hard Cheese made from Raw Goat’s Milk

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Abstract

Transmontano goat’s cheese is a traditional Portuguese cheese with Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) certification, made with raw milk from the *Serrana* goat, an autochthonous breed from Northern Portugal. The cheese-making is based on traditional methods with little modification over the years, and the final product is a matured, extra hard cheese with a slightly spicy taste. Because of its artisanal production, the quality attributes of *Transmontano* cheese can be quite variable.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the variability of selected quality properties between cheese batches, as well as the development of hygiene/safety indicator microorganisms (total viable counts [TVC, a.k.a. mesophiles], lactic acid bacteria [LAB], *Clostridium* spp., *Listeria* spp. and *Staphylococcus aureus*) in cheese during ripening, and how it is affected by milk/cheese’s intrinsic properties (i.e. pH, water activity [a_w], fat, protein and ashes content, and lactic acid concentration).

Raw milk and cheese during ripening were sampled from four production batches surveyed from an artisanal producer. Mixed models showed that the ripening process substantially reduced the variability of the physicochemical and microbiological qualities between batches of cheese.

The development of mesophiles in cheese was mainly affected by milk’s pH, a_w and initial TVC load as well as by initial pH and a_w of cheese, and to a lesser extent by protein and fat contents; meanwhile, the growth of LAB was mainly determined by milk’s pH, a_w , and initial LAB counts. The continuing drop of *Clostridium* spp. during ripening was regulated by all the intrinsic properties mentioned above, whilst the inactivation of *Listeria* spp. was highly associated to pH (from milk and from cheese at production day) and lactic acid concentration. *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 and *Listeria monocytogenes* were not detected in any of the analysed samples.

Keywords: Ripened cheese; lactic acid bacteria; *Staphylococcus aureus*; *Clostridium* spp.; *Listeria* spp.

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